

COMMON WORKPLACE ACCIDENTS BY WORKERS OF OIL INDUSTRY WHILE WORKING IN OIL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The present study was organized to assess noise intensity in selected oil industries of selected District of Marathawada region in Maharashtra state (Parbhani, Jalna, Nanded and Aurangabad). These oil industries were involved in expelling oil from cotton seed for the last 10-12 years. All the selected oil industries were established by small and medium entrepreneurs.

It was seen that majority of workers working in the selected oil industries were female. Majority of male & female workers were in 32-40 yrs. age group. Weight of majority of male workers was in between 50-62 kg and weight of female workers was up to 49 kg, while height of male and female workers ranged between 5.1-5.9 ft. Male workers had 9-12 years of experience of working in oil industry while female workers had 5-8 years' work experience.

It was found that cuts and lacerations are most common workplace accidents followed by burning in both male and female workers, always experienced by them. It was found that age of the male workers having positive correlation with frequency of cuts and lacerations whereas age of female workers was negatively correlated with frequency of slips, trips and falls, cuts and laceration and crashes and collisions, while weight of male workers was positively correlated with burnings.

Key words: Workplace accidents, workers, oil industry

Introduction

An accident may be defined as an unexpected and unplanned occurrence, which may or may not involve injury. The possibility of an accident occurring is present in every sphere of human life. (Penkey and Siddiqui, 2015).

According to Bouti and Allouch (2018) work-related accidents constitute a social phenomenon and one of the major problems all over the world, despite all the implemented safety control measures in any organization and the improvements in work-related safety which have been known in the last decades, things can still go wrong, and accidents and incidents still do happen. Ignoring H&S (Health and Safety) of workers cannot be the stepping stones to a good corporate sustainability strategy. The incidents rates have increased alongside the industrial revolution and the rapid globalization of the world. As a result, all sectors suffer from all types of adverse events ranging from deadly incidents to minor injuries at the workplace particularly in a hazardous working environment.

Oil industries has workplace that is downright dangerous. Accidents in the oil industry happen all too often. Rodriguez Kristopher (2017) opined that the most common type of accident involves workers being struck by an object or piece of equipment, resulting in 26 fatalities in 2011 alone. Fires and explosions led to another 12 fatalities during this period of time. It is not uncommon to see more than one worker sustaining fatal injuries in these types of accidents. The most common non-fatal injuries are lacerations, fractures and broken bones, burns, internal or external chemical burns, whiplash or other neck injuries, spinal cord injuries, concussions, brain injuries, paralysis.

Analyzing the statistics, we begin to see the most common causes of accidents in the oil industry—hazards that not only cost money but also continue to affect lives through injuries, hospitalizations and amputations each year. Hence the present study was undertaken to study the workplace hazards in oil industries of Parbhani district.

Objective:

To find out the common accidents while working in selected oil industries

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in thirty renowned oil industries located in the Marathawada region in Maharashtra state (Parbhani, Jalna, Nanded, and Aurangabad). These oil industries were involved in expelling oil

from cottonseed for the last 10-12 years. All the selected oil industries were established by small and medium entrepreneurs.

The study was conducted by survey method. Questionnaire was prepared to find out detailed information of the workers working in the oil industries. Information regarding common workplace accidents was collected through personal interview method.

Independent variables included in the study were age and weight.

Findings

It was seen that majority of workers working in the selected oil industries were female. Majority of male & female workers were in 32-40 yrs. age group. Weights of majority of male workers was in between 50-62 kg and weight of female workers was up to 49 kg, while height of male and female workers ranged between 5.1-5.9 ft. Male workers had 9-12 years of experience of working in oil industry while female workers had 5-8 years work experience.

Maximum percentages of male and female workers were educated up to secondary level. Monthly income of maximum male workers ranged between Rs. 6000-8000/-while that of female workers was ranged between Rs. 8000 – 10,000/-. It was also noted that maximum percentages of male and female workers were having 2-4 family members in the family.

Most common workplace accidents and frequency of experience by workers of oil industry while working in oil industry

Perusal in data table no 1 show the most common workplace accidents and frequencies of experience by workers while working in oil industry. It is clear from the table that cent percent of male workers always experience cuts and laceration while working in oil industry, whereas more than 80 per cent male workers always experience burning (98.18%), inhaling toxic fumes (83.63%) and crashes and collisions (82.27%). Minimum percentage of male workers always experience slips, trips and falls (43.63%) being hit by falling objects (21.81%) and explosions (16.36%).

In case of female workers, it was noticed that cent percent of them always experienced cuts and lacerations followed by burning (98.30%), equal percentage (89.83%) experienced slips, trips and falls and crashes and collisions and inhaling toxic fumes (88.13%). Less percentage of female workers always experience being hit by falling objects (28.81%) and explosions (11.86%).

Statistical analysis indicated significantly higher value of score for cuts and lacerations (3.00) and significantly lower frequency score was reported for explosions (1.30) for male workers while working in oil

industries. In case of female workers higher value score was noted for cuts and lacerations (3.00) and lower value score for explosions (1.16) while working in oil industry.

Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of most common workplace accidents experienced by workers while working in oil industry

Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of most common workplace accidents experienced by workers while working in oil industry is depicted in table 2. It is clear from the table that age of the male workers having positive correlation with frequency of cuts and lacerations which indicates that as the age of male workers increased the frequency of cuts of laceration were also increased.

With regards to age of female workers it was found that there was a negative correlation with frequency of slips, trips and falls (-0.249*), cuts and lacerations (-0.293*) and crashes and collisions (-0.249**) indicating that with the increase in age, frequencies of the slips, trips and falls, cuts and laceration and crashes and collisions were decreased while working in oil industry. It may be stated that because of acquired skills how to work in the oil industry there was decrease in slips, trips and falls cuts and lacerations and collisions.

Regarding weight it was found that age of the male worker is positively correlated with frequency of burning (0.337**) indicating that as the age of the male workers increased, they decreased the skill to the situation.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that cuts and lacerations are most common workplace accidents followed by burning in both male and female workers, always experienced by them. It was found that age of the male workers having positive correlation with frequency of cuts and lacerations whereas age of female workers was negatively correlated with frequency of slips, trips and falls, cuts and laceration and crashes and collisions, while weight of male workers was positively correlated with burnings.

References

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Table 2. Correlation between selected independent variables and frequency of most common workplace accidents experience by workers while working in oil industry

Sr. No.	Most common workplace accidents	Age		Weight	
		Male (N= 55)	Female (N=59)	Male (N= 55)	Female (N=59)
1	Slips, trips and falls	-0.124NS	-0.249*	-0.053 NS	0.199 NS
2	Burning	-0.022 NS	-0.056 NS	0.337**	-0.068 NS
3	Explosions	0.104 NS	-0.164 NS	-0.052 NS	0.044 NS
4	Cuts and lacerations	0.297*	-0.293*	0.055 NS	0.156 NS
5	Crashes and collisions	0.104 NS	-0.249*	0.058 NS	-0.180 NS
6	Inhaling toxic fumes	0.104 NS	0.199 NS	0.052 NS	0.064 NS
7	Being hit by falling objects	0.129 NS	0.163 NS	0.154 NS	-0.028 NS

NS = non-significant, ** = Highly Significant at 1 % level, * = Significant at 5 % level

Table 1. Most common workplace accidents and frequency of experience by workers of oil industry while working in oil industry

Sr. No.	Most common workplace accidents	Frequency of common workplace accidents									
		Male					Female				
		Total N = 55	Mean Average score	Always	Some time	Never	Total N = 59	Mean Average score	Always	Some time	Never
1	Slips, trips and falls	48 (87.27)	2.56	38 (69.09)	10 (18.18)	7 (12.72)	53 (89.83)	2.32	25 (42.37)	28 (47.45)	6 (10.16)
2	Burning	54 (98.18)	2.50	31 (56.36)	22 (40.00)	1 (1.81)	58 (98.30)	2.63	28 (47.45)	30 (50.87)	1 (1.69)
3	Explosions	9 (16.36)	1.30	2 (3.63)	7 (12.72)	52 (94.54)	7 (11.86)	1.16	3 (5.08)	4 (6.77)	52 (88.13)
4	Cut and lacerations	55 (100)	3.00	55 (100)	0	0	59 (100)	3.00	59 (100)	0	0
5	Crashes and collisions	48 (87.27)	2.50	35 (63.63)	13 (23.63)	7 (12.72)	53 (89.83)	2.32	25 (42.37)	28 (47.45)	6 (10.16)
6	Inhaling toxic fumes	46 (83.63)	2.43	33 (60.00)	13 (23.63)	9 (16.36)	52 (88.13)	2.27	23 (38.98)	29 (49.15)	7 (11.86)
7	Being hit by falling objects	12 (21.81)	1.43	12 (21.81)	0	43 (78.18)	17 (28.81)	1.37	5 (8.47)	12 (20.33)	42 (71.18)
		F Value = 2.65 NS, SE = 2.49 CD = 12.47					F Value = 0.33 NS, SE = 0.70 CD = 3.50				

Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages NS = non-significant